

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

FREE AND ENLIGHTENED CONSENT

Title: Correlating Code Smells and Refactorings in the Elixir functional language

Institutions: DCC/ICEx/UFMG and DPI/CCE/UFV

Responsible researchers:

- Prof. Lucas Vegi (lucas.vegi@ufv.br)

Assistant Professor at the Department of Computer Science at UFV

- Prof. Marco Túlio Valente (mtov@dcc.ufmg.br)

Associate professor at the Department of Computer Science at UFMG

This "Free and Enlightened Consent" contains information about our research. If you have any questions, do not hesitate to ask the responsible researchers.

Evaluation goals: This study aims to understand developers' perspectives on the ability of refactoring strategies for Elixir to remove code smells from programs implemented in this language

Survey information: We will ask you questions about your demographics, positions held, experience with Elixir, and your perception of code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir (i.e., the completeness of the removals).

Data collection and use: The data will be collected through this Google Form. It is estimated that each participant will need a maximum of 60 minutes to complete the answers. This data will be used to promote good practices to improve the quality of code implemented in Elixir. The identities of all participants, as well as their responses, will be kept confidential. You may choose to receive the preliminary results of the study, with the anonymity of data and participants preserved. The results will be published and presented at conferences and scientific journals without revealing the identity of the participants.

If you decide not to participate in the research: You are free to refuse to participate or withdraw your consent at any time. Your decision will not affect any relationship with the evaluators, professors, or the institution responsible for this research.

Compensation: Your participation is voluntary and unpaid. In addition, you will not be charged for participating in this research.

If you have any problems or any other questions about the research or the ethical aspects of this study: You can contact Lucas Vegi at any time at lucas.vegi@ufv.br.

Risks and measures to minimize them: When answering the questions, you may feel uncomfortable with questions that can bring back bad memories, fear of not knowing the answer, or even being identified. If you feel uncomfortable, you can pause completing the questionnaire and withdraw from participation at any time. The guarantee of data confidentiality ensured by the researchers is limited to the privacy policies of the virtual environment used for data collection (Google Forms). According to Brazilian legislation (Art. 9 of Resolution nº 510/16 of the National Health Council), in case of any damages resulting from your participation in this research, you will have the right to be compensated, under the terms of the Law.

Benefits: This research aims to promote good practices for improving the quality of systems implemented in Elixir, thus justifying its risks.

This survey will be carried out entirely remotely. In this way, [this consent term will be made available in digital copy through this Google Form](#). A copy of this digital consent will be kept by the responsible researchers and you will receive a digital copy via email after signing the term.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

E-mail *

Seu e-mail

Your full name: *

Sua resposta

Free and Enlightened Consent (voluntary agreement) *

I declare that I have read the document mentioned above and that I agree to participate as a volunteer, authorizing the anonymous use of the data generated by my participation for the academic purposes described above.

Avançar

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Limpar formulário

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Demographic questions

Select your country: *

Your city: *

Elixir experience time: *

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- More than 3 years

How many different projects have you participated in using Elixir? *

- Only one project
- Between 2 and 4 projects
- More than 4 projects

[Voltar](#)

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Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Perceptions on code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir

In previous studies, we cataloged [35 code smells](#) and [82 refactorings](#) tailored for Elixir. In the present work, we are proposing practical guidelines for removing code smells in Elixir using sequences of refactorings specific to the language.

For each code smell you are asked to evaluate, we will present the refactorings useful for its removal and explain their specific applications. These refactorings are listed in the order in which they should be performed when they are part of a sequence of operations. Specifically, when a refactoring should be applied on its own, it is listed with a bullet point (i.e., •). Conversely, when a refactoring is part of a sequence of operations, it is numbered to indicate its order (e.g., 1., 2., etc.).

Therefore, based on your experience, please answer the following questions for each presented smell:

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings removes this smell?

- Please rate the degree to which the refactoring sequence removes the code smell
- (1 = the refactoring sequence absolutely does not help remove the smell; 5 = the refactoring sequence completely removes the smell)

Notes:

- Each smell and refactoring is accompanied by a short description and a link with code examples.

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Untested polymorphic behaviors\]](#) smell? *

This smell refers to a function with generic, protocol-dependent parameters but without guards to verify its behavior. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Introduce overloading\]](#): We can use this refactoring to transform a simple polymorphic function into a multi-clause function, where each clause of the function is responsible for handling one of the supported data types.
 2. [\[Folding against a function definition\]](#): After transforming a polymorphic function into a multi-clause function, we can use this refactoring to delegate part of the processing within a clause's body to calls of other clauses of the same function.
- [\[Typing parameters and return values\]](#): Another improvement possibility for code suffering from this code smell is to use this refactoring to document a polymorphic function, making it clear which data types it supports.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Switch Statements\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when the same sequence of conditional statements—whether implemented with if/else, case, cond, or with—appears duplicated throughout the code. As a result, any new check added to these conditionals requires changes in multiple parts of the system. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Replace conditional with polymorphism via Protocols\]](#): Suppose the same sequence of conditional statements appears duplicated in the code. In that case, we may be forced to make changes in multiple parts of the code whenever a new check needs to be added to these duplicated sequences of conditional statements. This refactoring introduces polymorphism to data structures, thus improving the code's extensibility to handle flow controls based on data types.
2. [\[Converts guards to conditionals\]](#): The inverse operation of this present refactoring can be used to complement the previous refactoring operation, combining polymorphism with guard clauses in the implementation of the functions defined in the created *Protocol*.
- [\[Introduce pattern matching over a parameter\]](#): If a switch/conditional of a function is based on a set of numbers or strings that form a list of allowable values for some parameter (i.e., "type code"), we can use this refactoring to replace the conditional with a multi-clause function.
- [\[Introduce overloading\]](#): We can overload a function, transforming it into a multi-clause function, to eliminate a conditional.
1. [\[Extract function\]](#): Often the duplicated switch/conditional statement switches on a "type code". To isolate a switch/conditional in a *type code host*, start by extracting one of the duplicated switch/conditional statements into a new function.
2. [\[Moving a definition\]](#): Second, the extracted function should be moved to the right module.
3. [\[Generalise a function definition\]](#): After the previous composite refactoring, the moved function should be transformed into a higher-order function. One of the parameters of this generalized function will receive a function as an argument, responsible for defining the strategy of the internal conditional check.
4. [\[Folding against a function definition\]](#): Finally, all points in the code with duplicated switch/conditional statements can use this refactoring to replace the duplicated code with calls to the previously defined higher-order function.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Feature Envy\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a function accesses more data or calls more functions from another module than from its own. The presence of this smell can make a module less cohesive and increase code coupling. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Extract function\]](#): If part of a function calls more functions from other modules than from the module where it is defined, we can use this refactoring to separate the envious part into a new function.
2. [\[Moving a definition\]](#): If a function calls more functions from other modules than from the module where it is defined (e.g., the function extracted in the previous refactoring), we can move it to the module most accessed by it.
- [\[Remove import attributes\]](#): By using this refactoring, we can directly identify the origin of a function being called by another function. This way, we can more clearly identify a *Feature envy* instance, helping us to subsequently remove it.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Unsupervised process\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a library creates processes outside a supervision tree, therefore not allowing users to control their apps fully. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Moving error-handling mechanisms to supervision trees\]](#): Regardless of whether error-handling mechanisms are used or not, an unsupervised process can be moved to a supervision tree using this refactoring. With this transformation, the initialization of processes is delegated to a *Supervisor* and is no longer performed directly by the clients. This refactoring allows you to choose which module that behaves as a *Supervisor* to move to, or even to create a new module that implements the *Application* behaviour to act as a supervision tree.
- [\[Moving a definition\]](#): We can move the process initialization function calls (e.g., *GenServer.start/3*) into a *Supervisor*, delegating this task to it.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Large code generation by macros\]](#) smell? *

This code smell is related to macros that generate too much code. When a macro provides a large code generation, it impacts how the compiler or the runtime works. The reason for this is that Elixir may have to expand, compile, and execute a code multiple times, which will make compilation slower. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Extract function\]](#): When we have a *macro* that generates a large volume of code, potentially compromising compiler performance, we can use this refactoring to extract part of the *macro*'s code and encapsulate it in a conventional function that the *macro* will call. This approach reduces the amount of code that is expanded and compiled with each invocation of the *macro*.
2. [\[Moving a definition\]](#): After extracting the function, it may eventually be necessary to move it to another module to make the code more cohesive.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Shotgun Surgery\]](#) smell? *

This smell refers to a code with responsibilities spread across many Elixir modules, so that modifications require many small changes to many different modules at the same time. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactoring:

- [\[Moving a definition\]](#): When we need to simultaneously make a series of small changes in different modules, it's easy to overlook something important. In this case, you can use this refactoring to reorganize the modules, aiming to make them more cohesive so that all necessary changes are concentrated within their respective modules. If no current module seems like a good candidate to receive parts moved from others, we need to create one.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Duplicated Code\]](#) * smell?

This smell occurs when two or more code fragments look almost identical. Duplicated code can cause maintenance issues especially when changes are needed. Since multiple code fragments will have to be updated, there is the risk that one of them will not be changed, causing unwanted system behavior. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Defining a subset of a Map\]](#): It can be used to eliminate duplicated code generated by the manual access of values when extracting part of a Map
 - [\[Modifying keys in a Map\]](#): This refactoring can be used to eliminate duplicated code generated by the manual process of replacing a name given to a Map key.
 - [\[Folding against a function definition\]](#): When code contains expressions that perform operations already implemented in existing functions, we can remove this code duplication by using this refactoring, thus replacing the own expressions with calls to the existing functions.
 - [\[Extract expressions\]](#): When the same expression is repeated multiple times within a function, we can assign the expression to a variable and reuse that variable in all parts where the result of the expression is needed.
 - [\[Extract function\]](#): When the same code block appears in two different functions, we can extract it to a new function and call this function from both places where the code was originally duplicated.
 - [\[Reducing a boolean equality expression\]](#): When dealing with a boolean expression consisting of multiple equality comparisons involving the same variable and logical OR operators, we can eliminate duplicated code using this refactoring, thus utilizing the IN operator and a list containing all possible valid values for the variable.
 - [\[Generalise a function definition\]](#): When we have different functions that have non-identical but equivalent expressions, we can use this refactoring to create a new higher-order function that generalizes the equivalent expressions and subsequently is called in places where the expressions were originally used.
 - [\[Turning anonymous into local functions\]](#): When we encounter the same anonymous function being defined in different points of the codebase, these anonymous functions should be transformed into a local function, and the locations where the anonymous functions were originally implemented should be updated to use the new local function.
 - [\[Merging multiple definitions\]](#): There are situations where a codebase may have distinct and complementary functions. Because they are complementary, these functions may have identical code snippets. When identified, these functions can be merged into a new function that will simultaneously perform the processing done by the original functions separately.
 - [\[Move expression out of case\]](#): When the same expression is repeated at the end of all branches of a case statement, this refactoring can be used to eliminate the duplicated code.
 - [\[Remove redundant last clause in "with"\]](#): When the last clause of a with statement is composed of a pattern identical to the predefined value to be returned by the with in case all checked patterns match, this clause is considered redundant. Therefore this duplicated code can be eliminated using this refactoring.
 - [\[Static structure reuse\]](#): When identical tuples or lists are used at different points within a function, they are unnecessarily recreated by Elixir. Use this refactoring to eliminate these redundant recreations by assigning the structures to variables, allowing them to be shared throughout the code.
 - [\[Introduce import\]](#): When a module A calls many functions from a module B, the name of module B may appear repetitively in the code of module A due to fully-qualified name calls. This type of duplicated code can be eliminated by importing module B into module A.
 - [\[Widen or narrow definition scope\]](#): When we encounter the same anonymous function defined in different parts of the codebase, these functions should be transformed into a local function, eliminating code duplication by expanding the scope of the original function. This refactoring serves as an alternative to [\[Turning anonymous into local functions\]](#).
1. [\[Introduce Enum.map/2\]](#): When each element of a list is manually generated by repeatedly calling the same function, we can use this refactoring to eliminate duplicated code and make the code more idiomatic.
 2. [\[Transform to list comprehension\]](#): Optionally, after using the previous refactoring to eliminate duplicated code, we can use this operation to convert the call to Enum.map/2 into semantically equivalent code that can be also more declarative and easier to read.
 3. [\[List comprehension simplifications\]](#): Optionally, after using the previous refactoring as part of a sequence of atomic refactorings to eliminate duplicated code, we can also use this refactoring to revert the previous transformation, thereby retaining calls to the higher-order function Enum.map/2 instead of using list comprehensions.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

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Final remarks

Please add here any comment about our work and survey:

Sua resposta

Do you want to receive the preliminary results of this study? *

- Yes
- No

Uma cópia das suas respostas será enviada para o endereço de e-mail fornecido

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[Enviar](#)

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